

Incessant Strike and Quality of Job Performance among Academic Staff in the Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examines incessant strikes and the quality of job performance among academic staff of Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State. Incessant strike as a variable was used to evaluate academic job performance variables such as staff morale, staff teaching hours, research activities, and commitment level. The study was anchored on Karl Marx's conflict theory (1818 to 1883), and it employed a mixed-method survey design. A sample size of two hundred and thirty-five (235) academic staff from the university using the Taro Yamane formula was selected. Additionally, 20 senior academic and management staff were purposively selected for in-depth interviews. A self-designed questionnaire instrument was deployed to collect primary data from the sampled academic staff. The findings of the study revealed that incessant strikes have a negative impact on the academic staff morale, reduce the teaching hours of the academic staff, undermine their commitment level, and drive for research activities. On the whole, the endless ASUU strikes have a profound negative impact on the quality of job performance of the academic staff at FUU. By way of recommendations, the study suggested the following: The salaries and other remuneration of the academic staff should be upscaled immediately. The working tools and working environment of academic staff should be upgraded and enlarged in a way that motivates them to work. Lastly, the budgetary allocation given to tertiary institutions, especially the public ones, should be improved. Institutional managers should reward lecturers with outstanding performance to boost their morale for effective service delivery.

Keywords: *Incessant strike, teaching hours, academic performance, research Activities.*

Introduction

The role of the universities in human capital development, research and technological innovation cannot be over-emphasised. All over the world, investment in university education is a vital component of national development. Nations today increasingly depend on the knowledge, ideas, and skills that researchers in universities produce. Nations invest in university education because society expects it to contribute to producing highly skilled personnel in technology, engineering management and other professions (Dimiogbo and Akpunonu 2017). However, the education subsector, especially tertiary institutions in Nigeria, has witnessed incessant closures in recent times due to strike action by the academic staff, especially that of the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU). The frequent incessant strike action by the Union in Nigeria has remained disturbing and worrisome, as it is believed that there has been hardly any session in which ASUU did not embark on strike (Omeje & Ogbu, 2019).

The effect of these repeated closures of schools and academic programmes on the job performance of staff and students' learning effectiveness can better be imagined than described. Tertiary institutions in Nigeria have thus suffered tremendous setbacks as a result of incessant strike action. This has always subjected the students to pitiable conditions, disrupted academic programs, given students undeserved extensions in their study years, caused poor student concentration on academic programmes, and resulted in poor lecturer-student relationships, amongst others. Consequently, students' academic performance has progressively become so low while various forms of examination malpractices are on the increase. Presently, tertiary education in Nigeria seems to be losing its desired impact from this perspective. This is not because the lecturers are not intellectually competent but because of the porous and permissive socio-political environment in which tertiary education in Nigeria operates.

In light of this problem associated with the Nigerian educational system, labour relations in the university system are quite awry. In other words, the problem identified does not have a solution based on the relationship between unions in Nigerian universities and the government. Excessive workloads include heavy teaching schedules for lecturers, large class sizes, attendance for administrative duties, incessant strikes, school interruptions, student delinquencies, obnoxious institution policies, and poor. The working environment and other unfavourable conditions can contribute to stress. Such factors may affect the capacity job performance of the academic staff of universities. One of the most important and difficult problems for employers is determining the rate of wages and salaries. Incessant strikes can arise when employees and employers have failed to satisfactorily agree on their concerns. Industrial action represents the climax of unresolved conflict between employers and employees. Job performance is a concept that scholars have viewed as the degree to which a combination of duties are performed by academic staff of universities (Olakunle, 2011; Mbon et al., 2019; Odigwe et al., 2020).

Incessant strike is a generic term that covers all forms of industrial action undertaken by workers and employers to express their dissatisfaction in the workplace. (Anugwon, 2007, cited in Uzoh, 2015; Armstrong, 2009). Incessant strikes can be described as any activity that tends to increase tension between labour employers and employees. This means that the word incessant strike is related to employee dissatisfaction and demonstration of dissatisfaction rather than employer dissatisfaction. Strikes result in a total breakdown of cooperation between

employees and management. This may happen in the instance of industrial actions, which demonstrate themselves as strikes, go-slow and other coercive tactics and, at times, may even lead to violence. It may also happen in the instance of management when it takes the form of victimisation by way of lay-off retrenchment, closure, lockout, etc. The strike is workers' refusal to work as a protest for inadequate service or poor conditions. In the education sector, incessant strikes by academic staff can lead to student examination malpractice, corruption and other social ills that are as adversely impactful as corruption because of the damage to students' time, which makes it difficult for students to be fully and properly "baked" within the designated timeframe; as a result, products that are ill-equipped in both character and learning are turned out to the society. This research is targeted at examining the effect of the incessant strikes on the academic performance of students and the quality of job performance of the academic staff of the Federal University Otuoke. Essentially, the study seeks to examine the influence of incessant strikes on the morale of the academic staff, investigate the extent to which incessant strike affects academic staff research activities, assess the impact of incessant strikes on academic staff teaching hours and general commitment levels as it potentially affects the quality of their job performance.

Review of Related Literature

The impact of strikes on the academic staff of the Federal University Otuoke Chapter is diverse. Ige (2014) observed that incessant strikes in tertiary institutions in Nigeria have had negative effects, with the government, parents, educational institutions, and administrators having their share of the impact. Anyawu (2014) posits that incessant strikes have adverse effects on the economy. According to Anyawu, these effects include the suspension of the academic calendar, a conflict between the government and academics, corruption, laziness of students, an increase in crimes in the society, degrading the educational profile of Nigeria, loss of jobs, inactive economic activities and delay in registration of graduates with the National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) to mention a few. The incessant strikes usually have numerous negative effects on students. This is because the time that should have been used for teaching is instead spent at home due to the strike. As a result, it becomes impossible to cover the syllabus, and, in the end, students graduate with less knowledge than they should have acquired. This makes it difficult for them to compete with their counterparts from private schools. Many students in public universities study less, not necessarily due to a lack of intelligence or physical impairment but because of the unavailability of time. The lack of concentration for independent study arises from discouragement and demoralisation caused by incessant strikes.

In an empirical study by Ige (2014) aimed at stemming the tide of strikes in tertiary institutions, it was noted that for Nigeria to curb incessant strikes and advance tertiary education, effective government administration and proper orientation of tertiary institution staff are indispensable. Similarly, Osuorji and David (2014) examined the effect of incessant strikes on the academic performance of business education students at Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria. The study also sought to assess students' perceptions of the impact of strikes on their academic performance. Using a descriptive survey research design, the study found that incessant strikes by the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) have a negative impact on students' academic performance. This occurs as students lose concentration, as strikes act as distractions and disrupt their academic momentum upon resumption. Ayeni and Kolawole (2014) investigated recurring labour conflicts and strikes and their effects on achieving the goals of business education in tertiary institutions in Ekiti State. Using a descriptive survey research design, the authors concluded that incessant strike is a major challenge confronting tertiary institutions in the state. The study also revealed that strikes contributed to mass failure among students, primarily because they lacked sufficient time to study.

The history of strikes in public universities in Nigeria dates back to May 20, 1980, when a trade dispute was declared with the governing councils of universities in Nigeria. The dispute demanded improved funding for universities, academic freedom and autonomy, and the establishment of a special body to review the conditions of service for university staff. According to Anonaba (2015), in 1992, members of the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) declared an industrial dispute over the gross underfunding of universities in Nigeria, poor conditions of service for academic staff, university autonomy, and the need for academic freedom. The strike led to the introduction of a separate salary scale, tagged the University Academic Staff Salary (UASS), which the government later approved. More recently, ASUU declared a strike over the non-implementation of agreements reached with the Federal Government in 2000. This strike lasted for almost six months and was suspended during the last week of December 2013. These are just a few instances of strikes that have occurred in tertiary institutions in Nigeria (Nwankwo, 2000; Obe, 2003; Ige, 2014).

Akpala (1992) identified the causes of industrial disputes as economic, moral, political, and job-related factors. Regarding economic causes, he linked them to the improper adjustment of wages to the cost of living, the system of labour rewards (in cash, kind, or both), and working

conditions, including working hours. Ajewole (2014) further stated that industrial disputes in Nigerian tertiary institutions arise from poor infrastructure, low salaries, the government's failure to implement agreements with staff unions, frequent fuel price hikes, and demands for the reinstatement of sacked ASUU members, among others. Moral and political causes, according to Akpala, include employers' failure to ensure workers' welfare both on and off the job. Political disputes often involve union jurisdiction, function demarcation, recruitment issues, and employers' recognition of workers' organisations and leaders (Olaruwaju, 2004; Omolewe, 2017; Omeje, 2019). Various factors can trigger industrial conflicts between workers and management, some work-related and others independent of the job. In many cases, academic staff unions and affiliated bodies are sidelined in policymaking, leading to unfavourable industrial relations.

Theoretical Framework

Incessant strikes have been analysed through various theoretical perspectives, with scholars identifying the Marxist conflict theory as one of the most relevant for understanding and explaining such disputes.

Marxist Conflict Theory

Karl Marx, a German philosopher, economist, historian, political theorist, sociologist, and socialist, developed the conflict theory in 1882. He argued that conflict is an inevitable aspect of social existence, stemming from inequalities in power and economic wealth inherent in capitalist societies. Marxism holds that human societies develop through class struggle, primarily between the ruling class (bourgeoisie), who control the means of production, and the working class (proletariat), who sell their labour in exchange for wages. Marx predicted that capitalism would create internal tensions, leading to its eventual collapse to be replaced by a new system. He advocated for organised revolutionary action by the working class to dismantle capitalism and achieve socio-economic emancipation. Many philosophers agree that conflict is a natural part of society. It arises not only from competing interests within organisations but also from the broader division between those who own or manage production and those who rely solely on their labor for survival. Industrial conflict is thus viewed as synonymous with political and social unrest. Conflict theorists argue that trade unions emerge as a natural response to worker exploitation, as it is often difficult and risky for employees to voice grievances directly to management. While there may be temporary stability in industrial relations, institutions of joint regulation ultimately sustain capitalism rather than challenge it (Dessler, 2003; Arikewuyo, 2004; Wokoma, 2010).

The Marxist approach suggests that class conflict is necessary for social change. It bridges the gap between the economically dominant class and the dependent working class. Unlike pluralists, who see workplace conflict as an inevitable part of any organisation, Marxists argue that it is a direct consequence of capitalism. Adversarial relations in the workplace are simply a reflection of broader class struggles. According to Marxian analysis, workplace conflicts arise from power struggles between workers and employers over control of various aspects of work (Fashoyin, 2007; Alabi, 2007; Ogbette et al., 2017). In relation to this study, the theory explains why industrial conflicts persist—because those in power (the government and its agents) seek to control university staff's conditions of service. The struggle between the bourgeoisie (government) and the proletariat (university staff) over resources such as salaries and benefits fuels conflict, leading to strikes. These strikes disrupt academic activities, leaving students as the primary victims. A disrupted academic calendar negatively affects students' interest and engagement, ultimately leading to poor academic performance.

This theory is relevant to the study as industrial relations in Nigeria remain imbalanced and antagonistic, often favouring capital over labour. Trade unions, such as the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU), serve as both a response to government exploitation and a tool for pushing revolutionary social change in the workplace. However, rather than seeking to overthrow capitalism, unions focus on improving workers' conditions within the existing system. For Marxists, all strikes are inherently political. Due to its ability to explain the nature and persistence of industrial conflict, this theory is adopted for the study. Employers hold excessive power at the expense of workers, leading to disputes over work relations and control. While capitalists aim to purchase labour at the lowest possible cost, workers seek higher wages for survival (Fajana, 2000). This struggle between labour and capital remains at the heart of industrial disputes.

Methods

This study adopted mixed-method survey research that embraces the combination of quantitative and qualitative analysis for triangulation. The sample size is 235 academic staff arrived at using the Taro Yamane sample size determination. This is in addition to about 20 top management academic staff purposively selected across the faculties and departments as well as units in the university. The researchers used a combination of simple random sampling techniques and the purposive non-probability sampling technique to select the respondents across the various faculties and departments. Research tools used in presenting and analysing

the data include frequency distribution and percentage tables for the quantitative data, as well as the thematic approach in delivering the excerpts from the in-depth interviews.

Results and Discussion

This section covers the presentation and analysis of data collected from the fieldwork regarding incessant strikes and quality of job performance.

Table 1: Impact of incessant strike on work Morale of Academic Staff

S/N	Item Statement	SA	A	D	SD	U	T
1	My excitement level to work was reduced during the prolonged strike	80 (34.5%)	70 (30.2%)	45 (19.4%)	20 (8.62%)	17 (7.33%)	232 (100%)
2	I get depressed and demotivated to work whenever there is industrial action or strike	90 (38.8%)	60 (2.59%)	40 (17.2%)	32 (13.8%)	10 (4.31%)	232 (100%)
3	The long strike has caused me to think of changing job	100 (43.1%)	60 (25.9%)	50 (21.6%)	12 (5.17%)	10 (4.31%)	232 (100%)
4	My morale level drops sharply during any strike action	90 (38.8%)	70 (30.2%)	32 (13.8%)	30 (12.9%)	10 (4.31%)	232 (100%)
5	Does the incessant strike affect your work morale in any way	110 (47.4%)	75 (32.3%)	22 (9.49%)	20 (8.62%)	5 (2.16%)	232 (100%)
6	I felt discouraged and lost interest in my profession during the long industrial strike.	90 (38.8%)	80 (34.5%)	40 (17.2%)	12 (5.17%)	10 (4.31%)	232 (100%)

Source: field survey 2024

Table 1 above highlights the significant negative impact of incessant strikes on the work morale of academic staff. A considerable majority of respondents (64.7%) agreed that their excitement for work diminishes during prolonged strikes, while 65.5% reported feeling depressed and demotivated during industrial actions. Furthermore, 69% of respondents admitted that prolonged strikes have made them consider changing jobs, indicating a potential brain drain in academia. Additionally, 69% acknowledged that their morale sharply declines during strike actions, and an overwhelming 79.7% agreed that strikes negatively impact their overall work morale. Moreover, 73.3% of respondents expressed feelings of discouragement and a loss of interest in their profession due to prolonged industrial actions. These findings suggest that frequent strikes not only disrupt academic activities but also significantly lower motivation and job satisfaction among lecturers, potentially affecting the quality of education and retention of skilled personnel in the sector.

Below are excerpts from the in-depth interview section conducted on some selected academic management staff at the Federal University Otuoke.

“Increased strike action in Nigeria has become a norm in Nigerian universities, which has negative impacts, especially on the work morale of teaching staff. This is because, most of the time, when the strike is on, their salary is withheld or stopped for several months, which decreases the spirit and strength of academic staff to do meaningful research work.

(IDI 49 Years, Head of Department Physics- 2024) ”

Strike has a lot of impact on the work morale of academic staff in the sense that it reduces the excitement level to work and affect the work morale of academic staff

(IDI 56 Years, Head of Department of Microbiology-2024)

During the period of the strike, the academic staff felt discouraged and lost interest in their profession, which triggered thoughts of changing jobs. The academic staff's work morale level drops sharply during any strike action, and they are depressed and demotivated to work whenever there is industrial action.

(IDI 50 Years, Head of Department Chemistry-2024)

The frequent occurrence of incessant strikes in the university has some impact on the academic staff, such as dissatisfaction with wages, bad social conditions, fatigue, frustration at work, and discontent and aggressiveness.

(IDI female, 51 Years Head of Department Statistics-2024)

Table 2: Effect of Incessant Strike on the Teaching Hours of Academic Staff

S/N	Item Statement	SA	A	D	SD	U	T
1	Does the incessant strike hamper the quality of the lecturers' hours courses taught?	100 (43.1%)	40 (17.2%)	45 (19.4%)	17 (7.32%)	30 (12.9%)	232 (100%)
2	Does incessant strike hinder you from covering course outline	80 (34.5%)	50 (21.6%)	50 (21.6%)	32 (13.8%)	20 (8.62%)	232 (100%)
3	I often delegate my teaching responsibilities to students in the form of assignments due to incessant strike	70 (30.2%)	40 (17.2%)	60 (25.9%)	32 (13.8%)	30 (12.9%)	232 (100%)
4	I resort to crash lectures in a condensed manner due to incessant strike	130 (56.0%)	50 (21.0%)	15 (6.47%)	17 (7.33%)	20 (8.62%)	232 (100%)

Table 2 above reveals that incessant strikes have a profound negative impact on academic activities, particularly on teaching hours and course coverage. A significant majority of respondents (60.3%) either strongly agree or agree that strikes hamper the quality of lecture hours, leading to reduced teaching effectiveness. Similarly, 56.1% of respondents believe that strikes hinder their ability to cover the full course outline, which may result in incomplete knowledge transfer to students. Additionally, 47.4% acknowledge that they often delegate teaching responsibilities to students in the form of assignments due to the disruptions caused by strikes. The most concerning finding is that 77% of respondents resort to crash lectures, delivering condensed lessons to make up for lost time. This approach compromises the depth of learning and academic engagement, ultimately affecting both lecturers and students. These results underscore the urgent need for stable academic calendars to enhance the quality of education.

Below are excerpts from the in-depth interview session conducted.

Incessant strikes hamper the quality of the lecture hours and courses taught. Lecturers often delegate their teaching responsibilities to students in the form of assignments. Strikes also hinder lecturers from covering the course outline.

(IDI Female, 49 Years Head of Department Biology-2024)

Incessant strike hinders lecturers from covering course outlines and affects the quality of teaching, which leads to rush or crash programmes. Lecturers resort to crash lectures in a condensed manner due to incessant strikes. Lastly, it has effects on the quality of students that have been produced

(IDI Male, 55 Years Head of Department Sociology and Anthropology-2024)

Table 3: Influence of Incessant Strike on Academic Staff Work Commitment

S/N	Item Statement	SA	A	D	SD	U	T
1	Incessant strike undermines my work commitment.	100 (43.1%)	90 (38.8%)	18 (7.76%)	14 (6.03%)	10 (4.31%)	232 (100%)
2	I feel demoralised to do academic work due to incessant strike	100 (43.1%)	70 (30.2%)	32 (13.8%)	20 (8.62%)	10 (4.31%)	232 (100%)
3	My passion for academic work is negatively impacted due to incessant strike	80 (34.5%)	60 (25.9%)	40 (17.2%)	32 (13.8%)	20 (8.62%)	232 (100%)

4	I feel uncommitted to academic work during a prolonged strike	80 (24.5%)	70 (30.2%)	40 (17.2%)	12 (5.17%)	30 (12.9%)	232 (100%)
5	My interest in academic work drops due to incessant strikes in the university system	75 (32.3%)	50 (21.6%)	65 (28.0%)	17 (7.32%)	25 (6.47%)	232 (100%)

Source: field survey 2024

A brief analysis of Table 3 above shows the detrimental impact of incessant strikes on the commitment and enthusiasm of academic staff toward their work. A significant majority (81.9%) agreed that frequent strikes undermine their work commitment, while 73.3% admitted feeling demoralised in carrying out academic activities. Additionally, 60.4% of respondents reported that their passion for scholarly work is negatively affected, while 54.7% felt uncommitted to their duties during prolonged strikes. Furthermore, 53.9% acknowledged a decline in their interest in academic work due to the recurrent industrial actions in universities. These findings indicate that incessant strikes not only disrupt academic activities but also contribute to a loss of motivation, commitment, and long-term engagement among lecturers, which could ultimately affect the overall quality of education and research output.

Some of the excerpts from the interviews are:

The results of the in-depth interview study on the influence of incessant strikes on academic staff work commitment show that incessant strikes undermine the work commitment of academic staff and that passion for academic work is negatively impacted due to incessant strikes. (IDI 48 Years Head of Department Computer Science)

A strike causes the interest in academic staff work to drop and to feel uncommitted to academic work during prolonged strikes. It also makes the academic staff feel demoralised to do academic work due to the strike.

(IDI Male, 55 Years Head of Department Biochemistry -2024)

Table 4: Incidence of Incessant Strike and Academic Staff Drive for Research Studies

S/N	Item Statement	SA	A	D	SD	U	T
1	Do you do research work during strike action	12 (5.17%)	80 (34.5%)	20 (8.62%)	100 (43.1%)	20 (8.62%)	232 (100%)
2	Does strike action negatively affect your research work in any way?	95 (40.9%)	75 (32.3%)	25 (10.8%)	17 (7.32%)	20 (8.62%)	232 (100%)
3	Does a no-work-no-pay policy affect your research study or exercise negatively?	75 (32.3%)	65 (28.0%)	70 (30.2%)	12 (5.17%)	10 (4.31%)	232 (100%)
4	Do you have access to the university Internet during the prolonged strike?	90 (38.8%)	90 (38.8%)	20 (8.62%)	20 (8.62%)	12 (5.17%)	232 (100%)
5	Does incessant reduce your research habits and hours?	85 (36.6%)	60 (25.9%)	60 (25.9%)	7 (3.01%)	20 (8.62%)	232 (100%)
6	Incessant strikes induce a change in livelihood for survival, thereby affecting research obligations.	130 (56.0%)	50 (21.0%)	30 (12.0%)	17 (7.32%)	5 (2.16%)	232 (100%)
7	Does the incidence of incessant strikes affect your work performance?	99 (42.7%)	80 (34.5%)	40 (17.2%)	3 (1.29%)	10 (4.31%)	232 (100%)
8	Incessant strike undermines my efficiency and work effectiveness	100 (43.1%)	60 (25.9%)	32 (13.8%)	20 (8.62%)	20 (8.62%)	232 (100%)

Source: field survey 2024

Table 4 above highlights the adverse effects of incessant strikes on academic research productivity and efficiency. A majority of respondents (77.2%) acknowledged that strike actions negatively impact their research work, while 60.3% agreed that the "no work, no pay" policy further disrupts their research efforts. Additionally, 62.5% reported that incessant strikes reduce their research habits and hours, while 77% stated that they are forced to change their means of livelihood for survival, thereby neglecting their research obligations. Moreover, 77.2% confirmed that strikes affect their overall work performance, and 69% agreed that strikes undermine their efficiency and effectiveness. Interestingly, only 39.7% indicated that they engage in research during strike periods, with a significant 43.1% stating that they do not. These findings suggest that prolonged industrial actions not only disrupt teaching but also weaken research commitment, affecting knowledge production and innovation in the university system.

Based on results from the interviews, some of the participants note that:

Research activities are slowed down significantly during prolonged strikes as the government's no work; no pay policy seriously undermines the financial strength of staff to carry out any meaningful research during such a period (IDI Male, 57 Years Dean of Faculty Engineer-2024).

Furthermore, strikes cause a no-work, no-pay policy, thereby affecting the research study or exercise negatively and reducing the research habits and hours. Strikes induce a change in livelihood for survival, thereby affecting research obligations (IDI male, 48 Year Head of Department Mathematics-2024).

Findings

First and foremost, frequent strikes disrupt the academic calendar, which directly affects the ability of academic staff to achieve their professional goals. This disruption is particularly challenging for staff members engaged in research, academic publications, and other scholarly activities that require continuity and stability. When the academic calendar is frequently interrupted, research projects are delayed, publications are postponed, and the opportunity to contribute to the academic community is hindered. This can lead to frustration and a lack of fulfilment among the staff, as they are unable to meet their professional aspirations, and their morale to perform is negatively affected. This finding is consistent with earlier studies conducted by Ana and Adeleke (2018) and Archibong (2010).

Moreover, these strikes often result in a loss of valuable teaching time, compromising the quality of education delivered to students. Academic staff, who take pride in their teaching and the success of their students, may feel demoralised when they cannot fulfil their teaching duties effectively. The repeated interruption of teaching schedules can lead to a loss of enthusiasm and a feeling of disconnection from their role as educators, thus reducing the commitment level of self-driven academic staff. This finding aligns with previous studies conducted by Asuquo (2010) and Odigwe (2020).

Another significant impact of incessant strikes on work morale is the financial stress that comes with them. During strikes, academic staff may face delayed salaries or no payment at all, depending on the duration of the strike. This financial instability creates anxiety and uncertainty among staff members, who may struggle to meet their financial obligations. The stress of not being able to provide for themselves and their families can lead to a decrease in job satisfaction and overall morale. Additionally, the uncertainty surrounding job security during and after strikes can be a source of considerable stress for academic staff. In some cases, prolonged strikes can lead to discussions about restructuring, downsizing, or other cost-cutting

measures that may threaten the jobs of academic staff. This uncertainty can lead to feelings of insecurity and a lack of motivation to engage fully in their work.

The psychological and emotional toll of incessant strikes on academic staff cannot be overlooked. The constant state of uncertainty and disruption can lead to feelings of helplessness, frustration, and burnout. Academic staff who are passionate about their work may become disillusioned when they feel that factors beyond their control are undermining their efforts. This disillusionment can lead to a decrease in motivation, a lack of engagement in academic activities, and, in some cases, a desire to leave the institution altogether. Moreover, the strain of dealing with prolonged strikes can affect relationships among staff members. In an environment where morale is low, collaboration and teamwork may suffer as staff members become more focused on their struggles rather than working together towards common goals. This can lead to a breakdown in communication, a lack of support among colleagues, and a general sense of isolation within the academic community.

Incessant strikes also affect the relationship between students and academic staff. Students, who are often the primary victims of these disruptions, may become frustrated and lose trust in their lecturers. This strained relationship can further erode the morale of academic staff, who may feel unappreciated and undervalued. When students are dissatisfied, it can lead to negative evaluations of staff performance, further demotivating academic staff and impacting their sense of professional fulfilment.

Conclusion

The findings of this research reveal that incessant strikes have a detrimental impact on the job performance of academic staff in higher institutions. The persistent conflict between the government and the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) must not be allowed to jeopardise the educational future of Nigerian students. As observed, every university student aspires to complete their studies without disruption. Education in Nigeria must be prioritised, and the government must take decisive steps to address the root causes of these strikes. Nigerian universities cannot remain frequently shut down while both the government and ASUU expect to function without consequences. Beyond prolonging students' study duration, incessant strikes negatively affect their academic performance. Government policies on education and the inaction associated with them have contributed significantly to this crisis. This finding aligns with the results of Fashina's (2017) study. The negative implications of prolonged ASUU strikes in Nigeria are multifaceted. Several scholars have emphasised the importance of

industrial harmony between the government and academic staff to prevent further disruption to the nation's educational system (see Osuriji & David, 2014).

Furthermore, incessant strikes in Nigeria have had far-reaching negative impacts on various stakeholders, including the government, parents, educational institutions, students, and lecturers. This study has provided insights into how these strikes affect the job performance of lecturers and students' academic outcomes. Key variables such as staff teaching hours, morale, commitment to work, and motivation for research activities were all significantly undermined by recurrent and prolonged strike actions. Consequently, students' academic performance suffers, often leading to poor grades upon graduation. The economic implications of incessant strikes extend beyond the universities, affecting the nation as a whole. This study highlights the broader effects of these strikes on Nigeria's education system, economy, and security sector. Addressing this challenge requires urgent and sustained efforts from all stakeholders to ensure stability and progress in the country's higher education sector.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of this study.

- i. The government should ensure that lecturers' salaries are paid promptly. Additionally, institutional managers should recognise and reward outstanding lecturers to boost their morale and enhance effective service delivery.
- ii. Education policies should be dynamic and long-lasting rather than subject to change with every new administration. Each government should build upon existing policies instead of altering them arbitrarily. Furthermore, the appointment of ministers and commissioners of education should not be unilateral; rather, they should be selected from among senior career educationists to uphold excellence and maintain high academic standards.
- iii. Lecturers should be granted the flexibility they need to effectively carry out their responsibilities.
- iv. Students should develop the habit of studying independently during strikes, as this will help sustain their academic performance once the strike is over.

The government and non-governmental organisations should actively support the development of universities by providing essential infrastructure such as classroom blocks, well-equipped offices, and ICT resources. These investments will create a conducive teaching and learning environment, improve lecturers' job performance, and enhance overall academic quality.

Additionally, increasing budgetary allocations to the tertiary education sector will further strengthen the system and ensure long-term sustainability.

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